

LIVING-IN.EU

Smart cities and communities – EC policies

The Living-in.EU movement

Data space for smart communities

Local data platforms
-> interoperability

Local digital twins

The DIGITAL EUROPE Programme

LIVING-IN.EU

The European way of digital transformation in cities and communities

Over 150 signatures so far by Mayors, Regional and national Ministers

130+ supporters

I **sign** the Declaration because...

I **support** the Declaration because...

LIVING-IN.EU

Living-in EU signatories

Living-in EU supporters

Companies			
 Aiguasol Saest, SCCL	 Astrios	 BAVENIR	 Dassault Systèmes
 Daten-Kompetenzzentrum für Städte und Regionen (DKSR)	 DIGIE	 European Clusters Alliance	 FairFair.org
 Hafenstrom	 Innoconnect	 Kereval	 Martel Innovate
 Mobius Ecosense	 msg systems ag	 msg systems ag	 Murmuration
 OpenCitz	 Smart 4 Society	 SmartLampPost	 VERSES GLOBAL BV
 Rheologic	 Artech International	 Sirius NV	 Cumucore
 EGM	 METAPOLIS	 Privanova	 Die Strategiemannufaktur / The Strategy Architects
 Diehl Metering	 embeteco GmbH & Co. KG	 Urban Hotbed	 the urban institute® [ui!] the urban institute

 FM-Epizeiren	 Synelix Solutions S.A.	 EDC Debreceen Nonprofit Kft	 Crust Technology Ltd.
 OpenSky Data Systems	 Tangleence	 Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	 Environment Park SPA
 InBlenda	 LAND Italia Srl	 Latitudo 40	 LuxActive KG
 Cyclomedia	 Digital Twin Spatial Specialisten	 Red Plume Consultancy	 Serendipity
 Krakow Technology Park	 IRADIARE, Science for Evolution	 Atelierul de Idei Romania	 DunavNET
 Ocean Protocol	 Optfarm	 AnySolution	 Atos Spain S.A
 BIM6D Consulting & Performance SL	 BOSONIT	 Last Mile Team	 leanspots
 Movisat	 21c	 Celeris Advisory	 UrbanDNA

Living-in EU supporters

Association/non-profit			
 European Centre for Renewable Energy Gussing Ltd. Austria			
 FIWARE Spain			
 World Data League France			
 BRULOCALIS Belgium			
 Regional Economic Development Agency Stara Zagora Bulgaria			
 TIEKE Finnish Information Society Development Center Finland			
 ATHENS DIGITAL LAB - CITY OF ATHENS SMART-CITY HUB Greece			

 ATHENS DIGITAL LAB - CITY OF ATHENS SMART-CITY HUB Greece			
 Adventures of the Valparaíso Spain			
 Smart Innovation Norway Norway			
 Digital Innovation Zone EDIH Romania			
 Asociación Local de Economía Circular de Guadalajara Spain			
 MyData Sverige Ideell förening Sweden			

Living-in EU mission and vision

Create **cohesive, digital Europe** where every **city** and **community** can enjoy the economic and social **benefits** of a **green and digital transformation**.

Support cities and communities at the European level to develop, (re-)use and share trustworthy **solutions, technology and standards to accelerate** the European way of digital and green transformation at local level.

What's in for the local level

Unique access to information, funding and tools

Repository of:
aggregated knowledge,
policy guidelines and
technical instruments,
training programmes and
monitor and measuring
tools

Connecting you in the EU ecosystem

Effective collaborations with
EU, MS & all other
ecosystem players

Practical Guidance

We support you in your
process

Enhanced visibility and recognition

At EU level vis a vis all
ecosystem players

Cities can become a chair of one of our 5 sub-groups

Technical

Capacity

Financial

Monitoring

Legal

Concretely

- Minimum Interoperable Mechanisms (MIMs Plus) v6
- Fair AI standard procurement clauses
- Algorithm transparency registry
- Interoperable Europe Act
- Legal aspects of algorithm registries and data spaces
- LORDIMAS tool (measuring digital maturity of municipalities)
- Capacity building workshops (based on needs)
- Mapping of financial mechanisms
- Concrete funding mechanisms and their relevance for cities (e.g., 5G for SC)
- a list of needs from cities for the next financing period
- exploring EDICs

Concretely

Link with other projects:

- ❑ Local Data Spaces (DS4SSCC)
- ❑ Local Digital Twin toolbox (submitted tender)
- ❑ New European Bauhaus (DigiNEB)
- ❑ Testing and experimentation facilities (TEF)
- ❑ Net Zero Cities
- ❑ Covenant of Mayors

Stay tuned!

- Digital Maturity Assessment tool LORDIMAS (with CoR, ESPON) launched in October 2023
- MIMs developments (new iteration) – version 6.0 of 4 MIMs (1, 3, 4 and 7)
- European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC)
- Next signatory events and stakeholder forums

Join the living-in.eu movement!

JOIN HERE

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LIVING-IN.EU

@living_eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/living-in-eu/>

LIVING-IN.EU

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Thank you!

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